

Complexes of Zinc and Cadmium Iodides with Alkyl Sulphonium Iodides.

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The present investigation was undertaken with the object of finding if cadmium and zinc, belonging to the same group in the periodic table as and resembling in chemical behaviour mercuric mercury would yield a series of compounds, analogous to those formed by the interaction of trialkylsulphonium iodides with mercuric iodide (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 297).

The following compounds have been obtained by the interaction of alkyl sulphides or disulphides and alkyl iodides with cadmium and zinc iodides as enumerated below under (A) and (B) series respectively :

- (A) — (1) $(Et_3S)_2 CdI_4$. (2) $(Et_2MeS) CdI_3$. (3) $(Et_2PrS)_2 CdI_4$. (4) $(Et_2BuS) CdI_3$.
 (5) $(Me_3S)_2 CdI_4$. (6) $(Me_2 EtS)_2 CdI_4$. (7) $(Me_2 PrS)_2 CdI_4$. (8) $(Me_2 BuS) CdI_3$.
 (9) $(Pr_3S)_2 CdI_4$. (10) $(Pr_2 EtS) CdI_3$. (11) $(Bu_3S)_2 CdI_4$. (12) $(Et_3S)_2 CdI_2 Br_2$.
 (B) — (13) $(Me_3S)_4 ZnI_6$. (14) $(Me_2 EtS)_2 ZnI_4$. (15) $(Me_2 PrS)_2 ZnI_4$. (16) $(Et_3S)_2 ZnI_4$.
 (17) $(Et_2MeS)_2 ZnI_4$. (18) $(Et_2PrS)_2 ZnI_4$.

The chemical and physical properties of the above compounds have been studied and the constitutions assigned to them have been established from the following evidence.

The interaction of cadmium iodide on ethyl sulphide or diethyl disulphide and ethyl iodide leads to the corresponding product mentioned above. Thus it appears that the course of the reaction is as follows :

That diethyl disulphide loses one atom of sulphur is supported by the fact that when ammonia is added to the acetone solution of the substance, triethylsulphonium iodide separates out, CdI_2 being precipitated as $CdI_2 \cdot 2NH_3$.

The reaction of the sulphonium iodide is in fact strictly comparable to:

The conductivity of K_2CdI_4 and that of $(\text{Et}_3\text{S})_2\text{CdI}_4$ have been measured in aqueous solution and the two conductivities have been found to be of the same order, suggesting that the two compounds are alike in constitution. Further evidence in support of this view of the constitution of these compounds can be gathered from the following two reactions:

The products having the melting point 150° — 151° individually or when mixed, were found to be identical in both the cases. Had these been simple molecular compounds as represented in the equations above, they would have been different although isomeric. Hence the constitution would be $(\text{Et}_3\text{S})_2\text{CdBr}_2\text{I}_2$ or $[\text{CdBr}_2\text{I}_2]\dots 2\text{Et}_3\text{S}$. Several intermediate products (m.p. 90° — 100° and m.p. 100° — 118°) isolated by the above reaction have been found to be indefinite mixtures of the above compound with cadmium iodide.

The compounds resulting from the interaction of cadmium iodide, alkyl sulphides and alkyl iodides belong mainly to the series and are analogous to K_2CdI_4 and only a few to the KCdI_3 series and these again are strictly comparable to the corresponding compounds in the mercury series.

The formation of compounds of the type $\text{R}\cdot\text{CdI}_3$ (R = Trialkyl sulphide group *e.g.*, $\text{Me}_3\text{S}''$) is probably due to their greater stability under the experimental conditions, while compounds of the type R_2CdI_4 probably result through a decomposition of the triiodide thus

The separation of CdI_2 is not an uncommon occurrence in this series of compounds. Such a view is also supported by the work of Klinger and Maassen (*Annalen*, 1889, 252, 258), who found that cadmium sulphide, methyl iodide and methyl alcohol when heated in a sealed tube to 100° for 13—14 days, among other products give rise to a crystalline compound $\text{CdI}_2\cdot\text{Me}_3\text{SI}$, m.p. 167° — 168° . When an attempt is made to recrystallise it from alcohol it loses $\frac{1}{2}\text{CdI}_2$ per molecule and is transformed into the compound $\text{CdI}_2\cdot 2\text{Me}_3\text{SI}$ *i.e.*,

$(\text{Me}_3\text{S})_2\text{CdI}_4$, m.p. 185° . It is to be noted here that, with sulphides and iodides containing the alkyl radicals, compounds of the type $\text{R}_2\text{-CdI}_4$ are always formed when they are allowed to react in any proportion whatsoever.

These complex bodies easily dissociate when dissolved in water. A comparison of the conductivity tables shows that both K_2CdI_4 and $(\text{Et}_3\text{S})_2\text{CdI}_4$ dissociate on dilution into CdI_2 and 2KI or $2\text{Et}_3\text{SI}$, the conductivity values rising with increasing dilution. On treatment with ammonia in acetone solution, CdI_2 is precipitated as $\text{CdI}_2 \cdot 2\text{NH}_3$ and the trialkyl sulphonium iodide is decomposed.

Zinc iodide behaves like cadmium iodide so far as its action upon a mixture of alkyl iodide is concerned. The products have the general formula R_2ZnI_4 ; compounds of the formula RZnI_3 could not be isolated although in one instance, an anomalous result was obtained from the interaction of zinc iodide, methyl sulphide and methyl iodide, when a compound having the composition $(\text{Me}_3\text{S})_4\text{ZnI}_6$ was isolated. The formation of this compound can be explained by assuming reactions, similar to those given for cadmium iodide compounds.

It is not easy to ascertain why the methyl radical should have this sort of selective action. It is, however, wellknown that the first member of a series usually has anomalous properties.

The interactions between zinc iodide or cadmium iodide and (a) methyl sulphide or (b) ethyl sulphide and ethyl iodide take place violently and are exothermic. All these reactions proceed smoothly in acetone solution and are complete within half an hour.

EXPERIMENTAL.

(A) *Preparation of the compound $(\text{Et}_3\text{S})_2\text{CdI}_4$.*—(A) Cadmium iodide, ethyl sulphide and ethyl iodide in the proportion 1: 2: 2 mol. (ethyl iodide in slight excess) were allowed to react in acetone solution in the cold. The reaction was complete after three hours, when crystals of the compound separated. More acetone was added to the reaction mixture to dissolve the crystalline

compound formed. Ether was added to the solution until no more white crystalline precipitate of the compound separated. The substance was recrystallised from acetone. A mixture of the three components in equimolecular proportions (alkyl iodide in excess) gave the above compound but the compound $\text{Et}_3\text{S}\cdot\text{CdI}_3$ was not formed at all. (B) The same compound was obtained from cadmium iodide, diethyl disulphide and ethyl iodide in the proportion 1: 2: 2 mol. (alkyl iodide in excess) by heating them under reflux for 1 to 2 hours without dissolving them in acetone. A tarry viscous mass separated which was dissolved in acetone. The pure compound was isolated by dissolving repeatedly in acetone and precipitating each time with ether.

Each of the compounds (white monoclinic crystals) obtained from reactions (A) and (B) melts at 156° - 157° . Their mixed melting point is 156° - 157° . The same compound (m.p. 145°) was also obtained by Klinger and Maassen (*loc. cit.*) by heating cadmium sulphide with ethyl iodide and ethyl alcohol at 100° for 10-15 days. (Found: Cd, 13.06; I, 58.73; C, 16.44. $(\text{Et}_3\text{S})_2\text{CdI}_4$ requires Cd, 13.05; I, 59.2; C, 16.78 per cent.).

Analysis of the compound obtained from diethyl disulphide.—Found: Cd, 13.03; I, 58.69; C, 16.48 per cent.

Preparation of the compound K_2CdI_4 .—It was prepared by the interaction of potassium iodide (2 mol.) with cadmium iodide (1 mol.) in aqueous solution. It was purified by fractional crystallisation. (Found: Cd, 15.88; I, 72.01. K_2CdI_4 requires Cd, 16.04; I, 72.78 per cent.).

Measurement of conductivity of the compounds $(\text{Et}_3\text{S})_2\text{CdI}_4$ and K_2CdI_4 .—The conductivity was measured by the Leeds Northrup type of Wheatstone Bridge Box at a temperature 25° .

TABLE I.

Compound from ethyl sulphide.		Compound from diethyl disulphide.		K_2CdI_4 .	
Molecular concentration.	Molecular conductivity (r.o.).	Molecular concentration.	Molecular conductivity (r.o.).	Molecular concentration.	Molecular conductivity (r.o.).
·000154	443·4	·000141	463·1	·00013	524·6
·000077	482·0	·0000705	508·7	·000065	564·8
·0000385	539·4	·0000352	572·9	·0000325	595·4
·0000192	614·1	·0000176	669·9	·0000162	677·9

The conductivity data show (within experimental error) that the three compounds are of similar type. The greater difference in the case of the compound K_2CdI_4 is due to the greater mobility of the K^+ ion than that of the complex ion $(\text{Et}_3\text{S})^+$ in $(\text{Et}_3\text{S})_2\text{CdI}_4$, since Et_3S^+ is much heavier and more complex and sluggish in nature than the K^+ ion.

Preparation of the compound $(\text{Et}_2\text{MeS})\text{CdI}_3$.—Cadmium iodide, ethyl sulphide, methyl iodide in the proportion 1:1:1 mol. (methyl sulphide in slight excess) were allowed to react in acetone solution in the cold for two days after which the mixture was diluted with acetone and the compound was precipitated by adding ether. The precipitated compound was purified by repeatedly dissolving in acetone and precipitating by ether. It was finally crystallised from acetone.

The same compound was obtained from equimolecular proportion of the components.

Properties.—It is a white crystalline solid, m.p. 75° , highly soluble in acetone and also in methyl alcohol. It is isomorphous with the other members of the series. (Found: Cd, 18.69; I, 63.66; C, 9.85. $(\text{Et}_2\text{MeS})\text{CdI}_3$ requires, Cd, 18.73; I, 63.71; C, 10.03 per cent.)

Preparation of the compound $(\text{Et}_2\text{PrS})_2\text{CdI}_4$.—The components cadmium iodide, ethyl sulphide, *n*-propyl iodide in the proportion 1:2:2 mol. with the alkyl iodide in slight excess were mixed in acetone solution in the cold. The mixture was shaken at intervals and was allowed to remain for five days, when the reaction was found to be nearly complete. The compound was isolated in the usual manner by repeating the process of dissolving in acetone and precipitation with ether. The precipitated compound was crystallised from acetone.

From equimolecular mixture of the three components, the same compound was obtained; not even a trace of $(\text{Et}_2\text{PrS})\text{CdI}_3$ could be isolated.

Properties.—It is a crystalline monoclinic solid, m.p. 150° , very soluble in acetone, but less so than the methyl iodide compound of this series. (Found: Cd, 12.68; I, 57.05. $(\text{Et}_2\text{PrS})_2\text{CdI}_4$ requires Cd, 12.64; I, 57.34 per cent.)

Preparation of the compound $(\text{Et}_2\text{BuS})\text{CdI}_3$.—It was prepared in the same manner as the propyl iodide compound of this series, the components being cadmium iodide, ethyl sulphide and *n*-butyl iodide. The compound isolated from the two sets of reactions was

identical and not even a small amount of $(\text{Et}_2\text{BuS})_2\text{CdI}_4$ was obtained.

Properties.—The compound (m.p. 116°) is highly soluble in acetone and is the most soluble compound of this series. The crystals are isomorphous with the other members of the series. (Found: Cd, 17.46; I, 59.57 per cent. $(\text{Et}_2\text{BuS})\text{CdI}_3$ requires Cd, 17.5; I, 59.53 per cent.).

Preparation of the compound $(\text{Et}_3\text{S})_2\cdot\text{CdI}_2\text{Br}_2$.—Cadmium iodide, ethyl sulphide, ethyl bromide in the proportion 1:2:2 mol. were mixed together in acetone solution in the cold (with the alkyl bromide in excess). The mixture was allowed to remain at the ordinary temperature for two days and was shaken at intervals. The mixture was then diluted with acetone and was treated with ether until the precipitation was complete. The precipitate was again dissolved in acetone and reprecipitated in the crystalline state by ether.

The white crystalline precipitate thus obtained was recrystallised from acetone. The first crop of the crystals which separated within an hour melted at 145° - 150° . It was then washed with a little acetone, redissolved in acetone and the first fraction that was obtained this time after an hour was found to melt sharply at 150° - 151° . A proportion of it was also crystallised from methyl alcohol and the crystals so obtained were found to melt sharply at 150° - 151° , thus confirming the purity of the substance.

After the separation of the first fraction, two crops of crystals were also obtained from the mother liquor, but each of these fractions was found to melt within a wide range of temperature, the second crop melting between 110° - 120° and the third between 95° - 105° .

In precisely similar manner and under similar conditions, by taking the components cadmium bromide, ethyl sulphide and ethyl iodide, similar crops of crystals were isolated. The first one was obtained in quantity and it was purified as described in the other reaction and was found to melt at 150° - 151° .

Thus the compound isolated from the interaction of cadmium bromide, ethyl sulphide and ethyl iodide was identical with that obtained from the same sulphide and ethyl bromide and cadmium iodide, each having the melting point 150° - 151° and the mixed melting point was also 150° .

Properties.—It is a white crystalline solid. The crystals have monoclinic form. It is sparingly soluble in acetone in the cold.

Analysis of the compound obtained from cadmium iodide, ethyl sulphide and ethyl bromide.—Found: Cd, 14·36; Br+I, 54·31; C, 18·52 per cent.

Analysis of the compound obtained from cadmium bromide, ethyl sulphide and ethyl iodide.—Found: Cd, 14·38; Br+I, 54·34 per cent.

$(\text{Et}_3\text{S})_2\text{CdBr}_2\text{I}_2$ requires Cd, 14·53 ; Br+I, 54·18 ; C, 18·14 per cent.

TABLE II.

Conductivity in aqueous solution.

Temp. = 30°.

Mol concentration	...	·001033	·0005165	·0002582	·0001291	·0000645
Mol conductivity (r.o.)	...	397·4	431·4	457·4	494·4	548·3

From a comparison of the above table with Table I, it would appear that this compound is of the same type as those in Table I.

Preparation of the compound $(\text{Me}_3\text{S})_2\text{CdI}_4$.—Acetone solutions of cadmium iodide (1 mol.) and methyl sulphide (2 mol.) (a) were mixed together in the cold. To the mixture was added an excess of methyl iodide about (1 mol.). Gradually crystals of the compound began to separate. The reaction was complete in an hour. The compound was isolated in the usual manner and crystallised from methyl alcohol.

In whatever proportion the components were allowed to react, the compound $(\text{Me}_3\text{S})_2\text{CdI}_4$ was always formed. But the yield was maximum when they were mixed together in the proportion mentioned above.

(b) The same compound can be obtained from dimethyl disulphide, methyl iodide and cadmium iodide by heating the components at the temperature of water-bath for 5-6 hours. In this case and also with diethyl disulphide, the reaction did not take place at the ordinary temperature nor did the components react when their acetone solution was kept for days together.

The crystals obtained from both reactions (a) and (b) from methyl alcohol or acetone solution melted at 204°, which was also the melting point of the compound obtained from dimethyl disulphide. The mixed melting point was 203°-204°.

Properties.—It is a white crystalline (monoclinic) substance. It is sparingly soluble in acetone or methyl alcohol and also in boiling water, though a certain amount of the substance decomposes in this solvent.

The same compound was isolated by Klinger and Maassen (*loc. cit.*) by heating cadmium sulphide with methyl iodide and methyl alcohol for 13-14 days in a sealed tube at 100°. (Found: Cd, 14.44; I, 65.27; C, 9.3. $(\text{Et}_3\text{S})_2\text{CdI}_4$ requires Cd, 14.47; I, 65.63; C, 9.3 per cent.)

Analysis of the compound obtained from dimethyldisulphide.—Found: Cd, 14.45; I, 65.24; C, 9.27 per cent.

Preparation of the compound $(\text{Me}_2\text{EtS})_2\text{CdI}_4$.—Dimethyl sulphide, ethyl iodide and cadmium iodide were allowed to react in acetone solution at the ordinary temperature.

Properties.—It is a white crystalline (monoclinic) solid, m. p. 185°. It is more soluble in methyl alcohol or acetone than the compound mentioned above. (Found: Cd, 13.94; I, 63.11. $(\text{Me}_2\text{EtS})_2\text{CdI}_4$ requires Cd, 13.97; I, 63.34 per cent.)

Preparation of the compound $(\text{Me}_2\text{PrS})_2\text{CdI}_4$.—This compound was prepared (a) in the same way as the previous one using *n*-propyl iodide in place of ethyl iodide but in this case the reaction took 4 days to complete; and (b) by heating the components on the water-bath under reflux but with diminished yield.

Properties.—It is a white monoclinic crystalline solid, very soluble in either methyl alcohol or acetone, warm or cold, from which it crystallises slowly, m.p. 120°. (Found: Cd, 13.52; I, 60.74; C, 14.23. $(\text{Me}_2\text{PrS})_2\text{CdI}_4$ requires Cd, 13.49; I, 61.2; C, 14.46 per cent.)

Preparation of the compound $(\text{Me}_2\text{BuS})\text{CdI}_3$.—This compound (white monoclinic crystals, m.p. 130°) was prepared by the general method at laboratory temperature in acetone solution, the duration of the reaction being four days.

When the components were heated together under reflux on the water-bath for four to five hours without dissolving them in acetone, a tarry mass was obtained. By the usual process of extraction, a crystalline precipitate was obtained (from the tarry mass). The compound was recrystallised from methyl alcohol, m.p. 203°-204°. The yield was extremely small. The compound thus isolated was found to be identical with $(\text{Me}_3\text{S})_2\text{CdI}_4$ and like the latter it was also found to be sparingly soluble in acetone.

It may be that during the process of heating, dimethylbutylsulphonium iodide was formed and decomposed into methylbutylsulphide, giving rise to trimethylsulphonium iodide which, in turn, combined with cadmium iodide, yielding the compound $(\text{Me}_3\text{S})_2\text{CdI}_4$.

The behaviour of the sulphonium iodide has also been studied by Smiles (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1900, 77, 160), Klinger and Maassen (*loc. cit.*). (Found: Cd, 18.23; I, 62.22; C, 18.54. $(\text{Me}_2\text{BuS})\text{CdI}_3$ requires Cd, 18.3; I, 62.25; C, 11.76 per cent.).

Preparation of the compound $(\text{Pr}_3\text{S})_2\text{CdI}_4$.—To the acetone solution of cadmium iodide (1 mol.) were added *n*-propyl sulphide (2 mol.) and *n*-propyl iodide (2 mol.) and the mixture was kept at the ordinary temperature for a day (the alkyl iodide was added in slight excess). The compound was isolated in the usual manner by the use of acetone and ether. It was finally recrystallised from acetone. When the reaction was started with equimolecular mixture of the components, the same compound was also isolated at the end.

Properties.—The compound (white crystals, m.p. 151°-152°) is highly soluble in acetone, even in the cold and is in fact more soluble than the other two compounds of the series having the same alkyl radicals in the sulphonium iodide group. (Found: Cd, 11.85; I, 53.99. $(\text{Pr}_3\text{S})_2\text{CdI}_4$ requires Cd, 11.89; I, 53.93 per cent.).

Preparation of the compound $(\text{Pr}_2\text{EtS})\text{CdI}_3$.—The preparation was started with cadmium iodide, *n*-propyl sulphide and ethyl iodide in equimolecular proportion and also in another operation in the proportion 1:2:2 mol., the alkyl iodide being added in excess (about 2-3 g.). The reaction was allowed to take place in acetone solution in the cold for three days. The compounds that were isolated from each operation by the use of acetone and ether in the usual manner were found to be identical and to have the same melting point.

Properties.—It is a white crystalline solid, highly soluble in acetone, m.p. 77°-78°. (Found: Cd, 17.38; I, 59.26; C, 14.76. $(\text{Pr}_2\text{EtS})\text{CdI}_3$ requires Cd, 17.50; I, 59.53; C, 15.0 per cent.).

Preparation of the compound $(\text{Bu}_3\text{S})_2\text{CdI}_4$.—Cadmium iodide, butyl sulphide and butyl iodide in the proportion 1:2:2 mol. (butyl iodide in excess) were mixed up together in acetone solution and the components were allowed to react for two days. The compound was isolated in the usual manner by the use of acetone and ether.

Properties.—The compound (monoclinic crystalline solid m. p. 110°) is highly soluble in acetone. In fact, it is the most soluble of

all the compounds of the series having the same alkyl radicals in the sulphonium iodide group. (Found: Cd, 11.15; I, 50.05. $(\text{Bu}_3\text{S})_2\text{CdI}_4$ requires Cd, 10.92; I, 49.51 per cent.).

Preparation of the compound $\text{CdI}_2, 2\text{NH}_3$ —To the acetone solution of $(\text{Et}_3\text{S})_2\text{CdI}_4$, ammonia was passed until no more white precipitate was formed. The precipitate was filtered, and then washed several times with acetone to free it from any undecomposed substance. The filtrate was warmed a little to remove ammonia and then on cooling, it was treated with ether, when a yellow precipitate separated out. The yellow precipitate was crystallised from acetone. The yellowish crystalline substance (m. p. 145° - 148°) was found to be identical with the triethyl sulphoniumiodide, prepared by the interaction of ethyl sulphide and ethyl iodide. The triethyl sulphonium iodide being very hygroscopic, the melting point was not so sharp. In precisely similar manner, triethyl sulphoniumiodide was isolated from the compound obtained from cadmium iodide, diethyl disulphide and ethyl iodide, proving thereby the fact that one sulphur atom of ethyl disulphide was lost during its interaction with cadmium iodide and ethyl iodide. The white precipitate that was formed by passing ammonia was found to be $\text{CdI}_2, 2\text{NH}_3$. (Found: Cd, 28.2; I, 63.50. $\text{CdI}_2, 2\text{NH}_3$ requires Cd, 27.98; I, 63.75 per cent.).

Preparation of the compound $\text{Me}_3\text{S}_4 \cdot \text{ZnI}_6$.—Zinc iodide, methyl sulphide and methyl iodide in the proportion 1:2:2 mol. were allowed to react in acetone solution in the cold (methyl iodide being added in slight excess). The reaction was complete within half an hour, after which it was diluted with a little acetone and treated with ether. A white crystalline precipitate separated out. The precipitate was washed with a little acetone in order to free it from any unreacted zinc iodide and it was then recrystallised from acetone. The reaction was also started with the components in equimolecular proportion, but at the end, the one and same compound was obtained, not even a trace of $(\text{Me}_3\text{S})\text{ZnI}_3$ or $(\text{Me}_3\text{S})_2\text{ZnI}_4$ being formed. The same compound was also obtained by the use of dimethyl disulphide instead of using methyl sulphide in the above reaction. But in this case, the reaction mixture was heated on the water-bath for one hour without dissolving the components in acetone. At the ordinary temperature, however, no reaction took place.

Properties.—It is a lustrous white crystalline (rhombic) solid. It is sparingly soluble in acetone or methyl alcohol. Each of the

compounds obtained from methyl sulphide and methyl disulphide melts at 208° . Their mixed melting point is 207° - 208° . (Found: Zn, 5.77; I, 66.99; C, 12.39. $(\text{Me}_3\text{S})_4\text{ZnI}_6$ requires Zn, 5.73; I, 67.1; C, 12.69 per cent.).

Preparation of the compound $(\text{Me}_2\text{EtS})_2\text{ZnI}_4$.—It was obtained from the action of zinc iodide in acetone solution in the cold, upon methyl sulphide and ethyl iodide. The components were taken in the proportion 1:2:2 mol. (the alkyl iodide was added in excess). The reaction was complete after four hours. The compound was isolated in the usual manner by using acetone and ether. It was recrystallised from acetone. By varying the proportion of the reactants the same compound was always obtained.

Properties.—It is a white crystalline substance, m.p. 184° - 185° . It is more soluble in acetone or methyl alcohol than the triethyl sulphonium compound mentioned above. (Found: Zn, 8.51; I, 67.36; C, 12.48. $(\text{Me}_2\text{EtS})_2\text{ZnI}_4$ requires Zn, 8.61; I, 67.28; C, 12.72 per cent.).

Preparation of the compound $(\text{Me}_2\text{PrS})_2\text{ZnI}_4$.—Zinc iodide, methyl sulphide and propyl iodide were allowed to react in acetone solution in the proportion 1:2:2 mol. for four days at the ordinary temperature, when the reaction was found to be complete. The compound was isolated in similar manner as mentioned above. It melts at 132° - 133° . (Found: Zn, 8.28; I, 64.74; C, 15.09. $(\text{Me}_2\text{PrS})_2\text{ZnI}_4$ requires Zn, 8.3; I, 64.88; C, 15.33 per cent.).

Preparation of the compound $(\text{Et}_3\text{S})_2\text{ZnI}_4$.—The components, zinc iodide, ethyl sulphide and ethyl iodide in the proportion 1:2:2 mol. (the alkyl iodide was added in slight excess) were allowed to react in acetone solution at the ordinary temperature for two hours when the reaction was found to be complete. The compound was isolated from the reaction mixture by the use of acetone and ether. It was finally recrystallised from acetone. The same compound was also obtained by using ethyl disulphide instead of ethyl sulphide in the above reaction. But in this case the components were heated under reflux on the water-bath.

The compound obtained from either ethyl sulphide or ethyl disulphide melts at 149° and their mixed melting point is 148° - 149° . (Found: Zn, 8.12; I, 62.52; C, 17.43. $(\text{Et}_3\text{S})_2\text{ZnI}_4$ requires Zn, 8.01; I, 62.64; C, 17.75 per cent.).

TABLE III.

Conductivity in aqueous solution.

Temp. = 30.

Mol. concentration	...	·00473	·002365	·0011825	·0005912	·0002956
Mol. conductivity (r. o.)	...	438·5	4790	492·6	506·9	519·6

It will be evident from a comparison of Table III with Tables I and II that this compound is also of similar type to the compound in the other tables.

Preparation of the compound $(\text{Et}_2\text{MeS})_2\text{ZnI}_4$.—In this preparation too, the components zinc iodide, ethyl sulphide, methyl iodide were allowed to react in acetone solution in the proportion 1:2:2 mol. (methyl iodide being added in slight excess). The reaction was complete after three days. The product was isolated and purified in the same way as other compounds of the series. It was recrystallised from acetone. Not even a trace of the compound of the type KZnI_3 was obtained by carrying out the reaction with equimolecular proportion of the components.

Properties.—It is a white crystalline solid, m.p. 173°-174°, highly soluble in acetone, methyl alcohol, water, etc. The crystals are isomorphous with the other members of the series. (Found: Zn, 8·21; I, 64·22; C, 15·11. $(\text{Et}_2\text{MeS})_2\text{ZnI}_4$ requires Zn, 8·32; I, 64·88; C, 15·33 per cent.).

Preparation of the compound $(\text{Et}_2\text{PrS})_2\text{ZnI}_4$.—It was prepared by the interaction of zinc iodide with ethyl sulphide in the proportion 1:2:2 mol. (the alkyl iodide was added in slight excess) in acetone solution and isolated in a like manner.

Properties.—It is a white crystalline (monoclinic) solid m.p. 145°. It is soluble in acetone, methyl alcohol, water, etc., and is in fact the most soluble compound of the series. (Found: Zn, 7·62; I, 60·12; C, 19·65. $(\text{Et}_2\text{PrS})_2\text{ZnI}_4$ requires Zn, 7·74; I, 60·55; C, 20·02 per cent.). In all the reactions cited above, about 50-60% yield of the compound was obtained.

Preparation of zinc ammonia compound and isolation of the triethyl sulphonium iodide.—Through the acetone solution of $(\text{Et}_3\text{S})_2\text{ZnI}_4$, ammonia was passed until the precipitation of the white zinc ammonia compound was complete. The precipitate was several times washed with acetone. It was thus purified and then dried

from the filtrate; triethyl sulphonium iodide was isolated by the precipitation of the latter with ether, as in the case of the analagous cadmium iodide compound. (Found: Zn, 16.54; I, 65.94. $\text{ZnI}_2 \cdot 4\text{NH}_3$ requires Zn, 17.79; I, 65.63 per cent.).

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